

**WORKING ON SOUND PRONUNCIATION IN
MENTALLY DISABLED CHILDREN****O.T.Makhmudova**

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the theoretical foundations, psycholinguistic mechanisms, and effective methodological approaches of correctional and pedagogical work aimed at the formation and development of sound pronunciation in children with intellectual disabilities. The etiology of speech disorders, the specifics of phonemic perception, auditory-motor coordination, the level of development of the articulatory apparatus, and the stages of the correction process are highlighted. Practical recommendations, exercise systems, and speech therapy technologies are presented.

Slowing of speech development in children with intellectual disabilities creates serious limitations in their cognitive, emotional-volitional, and social activity. In particular, defects in the pronunciation of sounds negatively affect the fluency and clarity of oral speech. Many children with intellectual disabilities have phonetic-phonemic deficiencies, which, in turn, directly affects the processes of reading, writing, communication, and thinking. Therefore, in special pedagogy and speech therapy, the formation of sound pronunciation is considered a separate area.

Pronunciation defects observed against the background of intellectual disability are associated with various levels of psychophysiological factors: insufficiency of the central nervous system (insufficient development of the speech zones of the cerebral cortex, weak activity of sensory and motor analyzers, as well as a low level of articulatory motor skills (insufficient mobility of the muscles of the lips, tongue, jaw); underdevelopment of phonemic perception (insufficient ability to distinguish sounds, inability to distinguish acoustic features of sounds (voicedness, dullness, noise), difficulty in analyzing and synthesizing the received sound information); limited auditory function and auditory memory (slow process of auditory perception, low ability to remember and reproduce sounds); anatomical and physiological features of the articulatory apparatus (hypotonia or hypertonia of the muscles of the tongue and lips, improper breathing - nasal congestion, habit of breathing through the mouth and anatomical defects of the jaw system (open bite, narrow palate, etc.).

In the formation of sound, the mechanisms of breathing, phonation, and articulation work in harmony. In children with intellectual disabilities, it is precisely articulatory coordination that works weakly, the sequence of movements is disrupted, the transition from one articulatory position to another is slow.

Distinguishing, categorizing, memorizing, and separating a phoneme from the flow of speech is one of the most difficult processes for children with intellectual disabilities.

It is difficult to reconcile the sound image perceived through hearing with motor action. Therefore, pronunciation and listening are cultivated together.

In children with intellectual disabilities, pronunciation correction is carried out according to a specific sequence.

At the preparatory stage, there is work on correcting breathing (nasal breathing, correct exhalation), articulation gymnastics (exercises for lips and tongue), developing auditory attention, and forming rhythmic movements and speech rhythm.

Sound is produced by mechanical or functional methods:

- Visual method: showing tongue movements while looking in the mirror.
- Tactical-kinesthetic method: sensing articulation using the speech therapist's hand.
- Acoustic method: demonstration of the auditory properties of sound.
- Artificial stimuli: spatula, probe, vibrating devices.

Sound reinforcement in syllables, words, sentences:

- They become more complex starting with open-syllable words.
- Exercises for separating sounds and joining syllables.
- A series of words with the same sound (minimum pairs).

When introducing sound into speech, it is intended to use it in dialogic speech, to follow the correct pronunciation during storytelling, and to automate it through role-playing games ("seller-client," "doctor-patient," etc.).

Exercises for raising the tip of the tongue, rounding the lips, controlling the distance between the teeth: "Rose", "Watch", "Frog", "Table" and "Shell".

Correct breathing - the basis of correct pronunciation:

- Blow the candle slowly.
- The game of filling a pumpkin.
- Exercises for moving paper.
- Recognition of sound ("Which sound did you hear?").
- Comparison of sound (voiced-voiced).
- Determining the position of a sound at the beginning, middle, and end of a word.

Games increase motivation in children with intellectual disabilities: "What kind of animal makes a sound?", "Find Sound", "Soundbox", "Magic Mirrors".

Harmonious development of music, rhythm, and speech:

- Applause matching the line.
- Pronunciation of rhythmic poems.
- Orchestral games (sound-movement harmony).
- Mobile applications (SpeechKids, Articulation trainers).
- Video-model instructions.
- Sound recording analysis (audio-feedback).

Each child on the basis of:

- level of intelligence,
- stability of attention,
- auditory memory,

- state of the articulatory apparatus is assessed separately.

Initial, intermediate, and final diagnostics:

- Phonemic Perception Test
- Articulation test
- Bakhtin, Povorinskaya methods
- Vocabulary and Fluency Test

Individual exercises will be given to parents, and automation work will continue at home.

The formation of sound pronunciation in children with intellectual disabilities is a complex, multifaceted, and systematic correctional process. This process is closely related to phonemic perception, hearing, motor coordination, communication skills, and cognitive processes. The use of a special methodological system, articulation gymnastics, game exercises, phonemic development exercises, and multimedia tools increases correctional effectiveness. Individual planning of speech therapy work, regular diagnostics, and family support play an important role in the stable formation of sound pronunciation.

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